

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS.
PART VIII. SYNTHESIS OF 3:4-BENZODIPHENYLENE OXIDE

By J. N. CHATTERJEA

A synthesis of 3:4-benzodiphenylene oxide from 4-dibenzofuryl-lithium is described.

Kruber and Oberkobusch have isolated 3:4-benzodiphenylene oxide (I) (α -brazan, benzo [b] naphtho [2.1-d] furan, also known as 1:2-benzodiphenylene oxide) from coal-tar distillation products (*Chem. Ber.*, 1951, **84**, 831). The constitution of the compound was based on oxidative degradation to 2-phenylcoumarone and related products. The present paper describes an unambiguous synthesis of (I) from diphenylene oxide.

One of the remarkable properties of diphenylene oxide is that in replacement reactions, the position of the entering group is largely determined by the nature of the reactant and *not* by any orienting group. Thus, halogenation, sulphonation or succinoylation occurs in the position-2; nitration introduces a group in the position-3, whilst metalation with mercuric acetate or lithium alkyls proceeds in the position-4 (Gilman and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1415; Gilman and Morton, "Organic Reactions", Vol. VIII, Wiley, New York, p. 259; Willis, *Chem. Abs.*, 1944, **38**, 739). The metalation proceeds very satisfactorily with *n*-butyl-lithium affording (II) (Willis, *loc. cit.*) and as by appropriate treatment the lithium atom may be replaced by a variety of groups, it is of interest to introduce a butyric acid residue at the position-4 so as to obtain (VIII), which may lead to an unambiguous synthesis of α -brazan (I).

Carbonation of 4-dibenzofuryl-lithium (II) with carbon dioxide at 0° led to the exclusive formation of di-4-dibenzofuryl ketone (III) and the expected acid (V) was not formed even in traces (cf. Gilman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1258; 1939, **61**, 643). Interaction of (II) and *N*-methylformanilide furnished the 4-formyl derivative (IV) (cf. Wittig, "Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry", Interscience, N.Y. 1948, p. 570). This aldehyde on condensation with malonic acid in pyridine (aided by piperidine) yielded the cinnamic acid (VI), which on reduction with sodium amalgam afforded the propionic acid (VII). The orientation of these compounds

was established by oxidation of the acid (VI) with alkaline potassium permanganate to the known dibenzofuran-4-carboxylic acid (V) (Gilman and Young, *loc. cit.*). Homologation of (VII) by the Arndt-Eistert procedure afforded the butyric acid (VIII), isolated by way of the methyl ester. Cyclisation of the acid (VIII) with sulphuric acid or better by polyphosphoric acid proceeded satisfactorily, furnishing the cyclic ketone (IX). Reduction of the latter with lithium aluminium hydride yielded the corresponding carbinol which underwent dehydration and dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal, yielding α -brazan (I), identical with an authentic specimen, very generously supplied by Dr. O. Kruber. The compound has been characterised by a well crystalline picrate.

The U.V. absorption curve of (I) is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1
 α -Brazan.

A synthesis of (I) from 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (cf. Part VI, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 175) will be shortly communicated.

EXPERIMENTAL*

4-Formyldibenzofuran.—A mixture of dibenzofuran (8.5 g.) and *n*-butyl-lithium (0.05 mole) in ether was stirred at the room temperature for 12 hours in a current of purified dry nitrogen. An ethereal solution of *N*-methylformanilide (6.7 g.) was added dropwise to the mixture when a vigorous reaction took place. After leaving the mixture overnight, it was poured into an excess of dilute H_2SO_4 . The ethereal layer was separated, dried (sodium sulphate) and the solvent removed, affording the crude aldehyde, mixed with dibenzofuran. This was used in the next operation without purification.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 305° . (Found: N, 11.7. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_4$ requires N, 14.8 per cent).

Di-4-dibenzofuryl Ketone (III).—When CO_2 was bubbled into 4-dibenzofuryl-lithium, obtained above, at 0° , the product was a mixture of unchanged dibenzofuran and the ketone (III). Extraction with alkali did not reveal the presence of any acidic material. The ketone crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 174° . Gilman *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 643) report m.p. $172-73^\circ$. (Found: C, 82.5; H, 4.0. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{14}O_5$: C, 82.8; H, 3.9 per cent). The compound develops a yellow colour with H_2SO_4 .

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was very sparingly soluble in alcohol or acetic acid. It crystallised from nitrobenzene-alcohol in orange-yellow needles, m.p. $\geq 320^\circ$. (Found: N, 10.6. $C_{31}H_{18}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.3 per cent).

The oxime, prepared in pyridine, crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 253° (decomp.). (Found: C, 79.2; H, 4.4. $C_{28}H_{18}O_3N$ requires C, 79.5; H, 4.0 per cent).

β -4-Dibenzofurylacrylic Acid (VI).—A mixture of the crude aldehyde (6 g.), malonic acid (10 g.), pyridine (30 c.c.) and piperidine (1 c.c.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. The mixture was diluted, basified with NaOH and the volatile materials removed in a current of steam. The residual alkaline solution was freed from neutral matter by extraction with benzene and then acidified to yield (VI), crystallising from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 228° , yield 2.6 g. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 4.0. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.7; H, 4.2 per cent).

4-Dibenzofuryl Carboxylic Acid.—The foregoing acid (VI, 0.3 g.) was dissolved in alkali and boiled for a few minutes with a solution of $KMnO_4$ (0.6 g.) in water (15 c.c.). The mixture was clarified with SO_2 and acidified to furnish the acid (V), crystallising from aqueous alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 209-10. Gilman and Young (*loc. cit.*) record m.p. 209° . (Found: C, 73.6; H, 3.8. Calc. for $C_{19}H_8O_5$: C, 73.6; H, 3.7 per cent).

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected.

β-4-Dibenzofurylpropionic Acid (VII).—The acid (VI, 2.3 g.) was dissolved in dilute NaOH solution and reduced with sodium amalgam (100 g., 2%) which was added in small portions. After 3 hours the alkaline solution was clarified with charcoal, filtered and acidified, affording the acid (VII) as a colorless, crystalline mass, crystallising from alcohol (90%) in long blades, m.p. 148°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent).

The methyl ester, prepared by diazomethane, was obtained as colorless crystals, m.p. 22-23°.

γ-4-Dibenzofurylbutyric Acid (VIII).—The above propionic acid (1.8 g.) was dissolved in benzene (6 c.c.), treated with purified thionyl chloride (2 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine, and left for 3 hours. On removal of the volatile matter in vacuum on a water-bath, the acid chloride was obtained as a liquid mixed with pyridine hydrochloride. The acid chloride was taken up in benzene (6 c.c.) and added dropwise to a cooled ethereal solution of diazomethane (from nitrosomethylurea, 5 g.) and the mixture left overnight. On removing the solvent in vacuum, the diazoketone was obtained as a crystalline solid which was dissolved in dry methyl alcohol (30 c.c.), warmed to 60° and treated with silver oxide (prepared from $AgNO_3$ soln., 5 c.c., 10%) in small portions. The mixture was refluxed for 12 hours, treated with an additional silver oxide and refluxed for further 2 hours. The mixture was filtered with charcoal, concentrated and the residual oily methyl ester of (VIII) hydrolysed by boiling with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (15 c.c., 10%). On acidification, the butyric acid (VIII) was obtained as a gum which slowly solidified; yield 0.7 g. It crystallised from petroleum ether in colorless crystalline prismatic mass, m.p. 89-90°. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 5.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5 per cent).

*4-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-2-braza*n (IX).—The above acid (0.1 g.) was warmed at 175°-180° with polyphosphoric acid derived from phosphoric acid (5 g., 85%) and phosphoric anhydride (2 g.) for 45 minutes. The mixture was treated with ice, extracted with ether, washed with dilute alkali, dried and the solvent removed. The crystalline solid (IX) (70 mg.) crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 148-49°. (Found: C, 81.0; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.4; H, 5.1 per cent).

The ketone can also be obtained in presence of sulphuric acid (89%) at the room temperature for 18 minutes and then working up the product as usual.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. >305°. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

α-Braza)n.—A solution of the above ketone (50 mg.) in dry ether (15 c.c.) was treated in cold with a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (40 mg.) in ether (5 c.c.). After the vigorous reaction was over, the mixture was decomposed after 1 hour with iced HCl, the ethereal extract dried and the solvent removed, furnishing the corresponding alcohol (IX: -CHOH- in place of -CO-) in quantitative yield, m.p. 132°. It was mixed thoroughly with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.) (Linstead and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1127) and heated in a metal bath at 280°-310° for 2 hours. The characteristic odour of *α*-braza)n was perceptible. The mass was extracted with benzene; filtered through a column of alumina, concentrated and the residue (28 mg.) was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 102-103°, undepressed on admixture with an

authentic specimen. (Found: C, 88.5; H, 4.2. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{10}O$: C, 88.1; H, 4.5 per cent).

U. V. absorption: λ_{max} (in absolute alcohol), 3380 Å ($\epsilon=7450$), 3305 Å ($\epsilon=2640$), 3230 Å ($\epsilon=5050$), 3160 Å ($\epsilon=2720$), 2970 Å ($\epsilon=19500$), 2880 Å ($\epsilon=17900$), 2590 Å ($\epsilon=94100$), 2495 Å ($\epsilon=43100$), 2410 Å ($\epsilon=32400$) and 2100 Å ($\epsilon=24800$).

α -Brazan gave an orange-red picrate from alcoholic picric acid, m.p. 109-10° (Found: C, 59.6; H, 3.0. $C_{18}H_{10}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$, requires C, 59.1; H, 2.9 per cent).

The author wishes to thank Dr. O. Kruber for the provision of a specimen α -brazan obtained from coal tar.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
PATNA-5.

Received August 26, 1955.